

REVIEW ON ENHANCEMENT OF HEAT EXCHANGER BY MECHANICAL AIDS

MAZEDAN TRANSACTIONS ON
ENGINEERING SYSTEMS DESIGN

e-ISSN: 2582-8061

Article id-MTESD0602037

Vol-6, Issue-2

Received: 13 May 2025

Revised: 10 June 2025

Accepted: 17 June 2025

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16418064>

Citation: Savant, S. G., Dange, B. S., Londhe, V. D., & Thore, S. B. (2025). Review On Enhancement of Heat Exchanger by Mechanical Aids. *Mazedan Transactions on Engineering Systems Design*, 6(2), 166–169.

Abstract

The heat exchanger is an important device in almost all of the mechanical industries it is key element. Thus, many researchers in this area are working to improve the performance of the heat exchangers in terms of heat transfer rate. This paper is a review of passive augmentation techniques used in heat exchangers. The thermal performance behavior of tube in tube heat exchanger it is studied for wire coil inserts, twisted tape inserts and their combination. The research was done for constant/periodically varying wire coil pitch ratio. Some of them have varied 3 coil pitch ratios. The conical ring was also been tested. These inserts are tested individually and in combine form and results were compared. The Reynolds number is selected for allowing the inserts to be tested for different flow conditions from laminar, transient and turbulent. The new improved performance was found in the increasing order for inserts like wire coil, twisted tapes and conical inserts. Also, some of researchers have developed correlations for these inserts for Nusselt number as a function of Reynolds number.

Keywords: Heat transfer enhancement, Passive technique, wire coil, Heat exchanger, Conical insert.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heat exchangers are used in different processes ranging from conversion, utilization & recovery of thermal energy in various industrial, commercial & domestic applications. Some common examples include steam generation, condensation in power & cogeneration plants, sensible heating & cooling in thermal processing of chemical, pharmaceutical & agricultural products, fluid heating in manufacturing & waste heat recovery etc. Increase in Heat exchanger's performance can lead to more economical design of heat exchanger which can help to make energy, material & cost savings related to a heat exchange process. The need to increase the thermal performance of heat exchangers, thereby effecting energy, material.; cost savings have led to development & use of many techniques termed as Heat transfer Augmentation. These techniques are also referred as Heat transfer Enhancement or Intensification. Augmentation techniques increase convective heat transfer by reducing the thermal resistance in a heat exchanger. Use of Heat transfer enhancement techniques lead to increase in heat transfer coefficient but at the cost of increase in pressure drop. So, while designing a heat exchanger using any of these techniques, analysis of heat transfer rate; pressure drop has to be done. Exchanger has to be studied. To achieve more heat transfer rate in an existing or new heat exchanger while taking care of the increased pumping power, several techniques have been done in recent years and are discussed. Inserts like Conical tube a type of

passive heat transfer augmentation techniques has shown significantly good results.

2. HEAT TRANSFER ENHANCEMENT

Heat transfer enhancement is the process of modifying a heat transfer surface or the cross-section flow to either increase the heat transfer coefficient between fluid and surface to effectively maintain higher heat loads with a smaller temperature difference. I have treated some practical examples of heat transfer enhancement like fins, surface roughness, conical inserts and coiled tube, which are generally referred to as passive techniques. Heat transfer enhancement may also be achieved by surface, fluid vibration, electrostatic fields. These methods are often referred to as active techniques because they required the application of external power. Active techniques have received attention in the research literature some practical applications are very limited. In this section some specific examples of passive techniques. Increases in heat transfer due to surface treatment increased turbulence, increased surface area, and improved mixing or flow swirl. These effects generally result in increase in pressure drop along with the more increase in heat transfer. However, with performance evaluation and optimization, significant heat transfer improvement relative to an untreated heat transfer surface of the same nominal heat transfer area is achieved for a variety of applications. The increasing in attractiveness of different heat transfer enhancement techniques are

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benefits of industrial importance because due to heat exchanger offer the opportunity.

To reduce the heat transfer surface area required for a given application.

- Reduces the heat exchanger size and cost.
- Increase the heat rate of the exchanger.
- Permit closer approach temperature.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Wenguang Li, Sambhaji Kadam, Zhibin Yu [1] this paper carbon dioxide (CO₂) heat exchangers in refrigeration systems more efficient and compact, passive methods for heat transfer enhancement produced by tubes in various shapes were surveyed and assessed.

Ya-Ling Heetal. [2]: This paper investigated the heat transfer enhancement by using winglet twisted tapes were surveyed and assessed.

Ya-Ling Heetal. [3]: This paper investigated the heat transfer enhancement and pressure loss penalty for fin-and-tube heat exchangers with rectangular winglet pairs (RWPs) were numerically investigated in a relatively low Reynolds number flow. The purpose of this study was to explore the fundamental mechanism between the local flow structure and the heat transfer augmentation.

S Naga sarada, A.V Sita Rama Raju [4]: This paper shows the result obtained from experimental investigations of augmentation of turbulent flow heat transfer in a horizontal tube by means of varying width conical ring inserts with air as a working fluid.

S. Liu, M. Sakr [5]: This paper shows that conical ring inserts platform better in laminar flow than turbulent flow. In this paper other several passive techniques of enhancement of heat transfer such as ribs, conical nozzle & conical rings.

Subhankar Saha, Sujoy Kumar Saha. [6]: This paper presented experimental friction factor & Nusselt number data for laminar flow viscous oil through a circular duct having integral helical rib roughness fitted with helical screw tape inserts.

V. Vivek, L. viveknath& N. Vinayagam [7]: In this hydraulic experimental facility is provided for measurement of pressure drop & heat transfer coefficient in water flowing through a cylindrical annulus with single & double start helical tapes.

M.M. K Bhutiya, A.S. M Sayenetc [8]: This paper based on an experimental study on to investigate the air flow friction & heat transfer characteristics in a circular tube fitted with double counter conical ring inserts of different twist ratio for turbulent regime. The use of double counter conical ring inserts provided significant augmentation of heat transfer by causing a high pressure drop increase.

Classification Of Augmentation Techniques

- It is broadly classified into three different categories.
- Passive Techniques
- Active Techniques

- Compound Techniques.

Passive Techniques

These techniques do not require any direct input of external power; rather than use it from the system itself which leads to an increase in the fluid pressure drop. They use surface or geometrical modifications to the flow channel by inserts or additional devices. Heat transfer augmentation techniques can be achieved by using;

- Treated Surfaces
- Rough surfaces
- Extended surfaces
- Displaced enhancement devices
- Swirl flow devices
- Coiled tubes
- Surface tension devices
- Additives for liquids
- Additives for gases

Active Techniques

In this technique, an external power is used to facilitate the desired flow modification and improvement in the heat transfer rate. The augmentation of heat transfer by this method can be achieved by following:

- Suctions
- Surface vibrations
- Fluid vibrations
- Electrostatic fields
- Injections
- Mechanical Aids

Advantages Of Augmentation Techniques

The benefits which can be seen by installing tabulators can be seen below again this will depend on the type of heat exchanger as well as the type of issues which you might be trying to overcome.

- Improved Heat Transfer
- Heat Transfer Coefficient improvement by over 3 times
- Improved Performance within Heat Exchangers
- Reduced plot area needed for new Heat Exchangers
- Convert Laminar Flow to Turbulent Flow

Reduction in Fouling

- Reduction in Film Build up
- Reduction of costs during Downtime
- Constant uniform temperature
- Reduces gradients which can cause thermal breakdown

4. MECHANICAL AIDS FOR HEAT TRANSFER ENHANCEMENT

Mechanical aids are active or passive devices introduced into heat exchangers to alter the flow structure. They enhance heat transfer mainly by: Inducing secondary flows, Interrupting boundary layer development, increasing surface area contact, Improving fluid mixing.

Common types of mechanical aids include:

Twisted Tapes

Twisted tapes are metal strips twisted along their length and inserted into the flow passage. They create a swirling flow that continuously disrupts the thermal boundary layer, leading to higher convective heat transfer coefficients. Modified twisted tapes (such as perforated, serrated, or double twisted tapes) offer further performance improvements.

Wire Coil Inserts

Wire coils inserted into tubes generate centrifugal forces that enhance mixing and delay boundary layer formation. They are simple to install and can substantially improve the heat transfer with moderate pressure drop penalties.

Extended Surfaces (Fins)

Adding fins inside or outside the heat exchanger tubes increases the effective surface area for heat transfer. Corrugated fins, louvered fins, or pin fins also induce secondary flows and turbulence, improving heat transfer efficiency.

Helical Inserts

Helical inserts generate a helical flow path, forcing the fluid to move tangentially and axially, increasing the heat transfer rate. They are especially useful in laminar and transitional flow regimes.

Surface Protrusions

Small ribs, dimples, or vortex generators added to the heat exchange surfaces promote local turbulence and disrupt the boundary layer. Protrusions can be optimally designed to balance heat transfer enhancement against pressure drop penalties.

Rotating Devices

In some designs, parts of the exchanger, like tubes or inserts, are rotated mechanically during operation. This active method can greatly enhance heat transfer but usually involves higher operational complexity and energy consumption.

Performance Metrics

When evaluating mechanical aids, the following parameters are critical:

- Nusselt number (Nu): Indicator of convective heat transfer enhancement.
- Friction factor (f): Relates to the pressure drop and energy required to maintain fluid flow.
- Thermal performance factor (TPF): Compares the gain in heat transfer to the penalty in pressure drop.

- Effectiveness-NTU analysis: Especially important for compact and recuperative heat exchangers.

Challenges and Trade-offs

While mechanical aids offer substantial heat transfer enhancement, they also introduce certain challenges:

- Increased pressure drops leading to higher pumping power.
- Complexity in manufacturing and maintenance.
- Risk of fouling, especially in complex structures.
- Cost versus performance trade-offs.

Thus, careful optimization and application-specific design are critical for achieving the best results.

Recent Developments

- Hybrid aids: Combining multiple techniques like twisted tape with surface roughness.
- Additive manufacturing: Allowing complex geometries that were previously impossible.
- Smart materials: Using shape memory alloys that adapt their configuration under different conditions.

Figure 1 Details of conical inserts

5. NOMENCLATURE

D = Major diameter (outer)

d = minor diameter (inner)

L = length of conical inserts

Basic Mathematical Expressions and Correlations

- The **Nusselt number** represents the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer across a boundary.

$$Nu = \frac{hL}{k}$$

- h : Convective heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$)
- l : Characteristic length (m)
- k : Thermal conductivity of the fluid ($\text{W}/\text{m} \cdot \text{K}$)

- **Reynolds Number (Re)**: Represents the ratio of inertial to viscous forces in a fluid flow.

$$Re = \frac{\rho \mu L}{\mu} = \frac{\mu L}{\nu}$$

- ρ : Fluid density (kg/m^3)
- u : Flow velocity (m/s)
- L : Characteristic length or hydraulic diameter (m)
- μ : Dynamic viscosity ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)
- ν : Kinematic viscosity (m^2/s)
- **Prandtl number:** The Prandtl number is a dimensionless quantity that represents the ratio of momentum diffusivity to thermal diffusivity in a fluid.
- **Nusselt Number Correlations (Nu vs Re)**
 - Dittus-Boelter Equation (for turbulent flow, $\text{Re} > 10000$ $n=0.4$ for heating, $n=0.3$ for cooling Pr : Prandtl number)
- **Laminar Flow in Pipe:** $\text{Nu}=3.66$ (for fully developed, constant wall temperature).
- **Thermal Performance Factor (TPF)** Also called Performance Evaluation Criterion (PEC), used to compare enhanced and standard heat transfer surfaces:

$$\text{TPF} = \frac{\text{Nu}}{\text{Nu}_0} \left(\frac{f}{f_0} \right)^{1/3}$$

- Nu , f : Enhanced surface
- Nu_0 , f_0 : (Baseline (smooth surface)) A $\text{TPF} > 1$ indicates enhancement in thermal performance

Displaced Enhancement Devices

Several types of inserts which are classified as displaced enhancement devices including static mixer elements, metallic mesh, wire matrix inserts, rings or round balls. Rings and round balls have efficient heat transfer improvements, but the friction factors are high. Most of the devices are effective only in laminar flows. Spiral brush inserts in short channels with turbulent flows have high heat transfer coefficient can be improved as much as 8.5 times of smooth tube.

Figure 2 Conical Ring inserts in circular tube

- Diverging Ring
- Converging Ring,
- Converging and Diverging Rings

6. CONCLUSION

Mechanical aids offer a reliable and effective means for enhancing the performance of heat exchangers. Though there are associated drawbacks such as increased pressure

drop and complexity, advancements in design and materials are progressively overcoming these limitations. Future research is likely to focus on optimizing designs for specific applications, minimizing energy penalties, and leveraging modern fabrication techniques.

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